

*Proceedings of the 17th International Conference
on Computational and Mathematical Methods
in Science and Engineering, CMMSE 2017
4–8 July, 2017.*

A Distributed and Flexible Platform for Large-Scale Data Storage in HPC Systems

Cristina Rodríguez-Quintana¹, Antonio F. Díaz¹, Julio Ortega¹, Raúl H. Palacios², Juan José Escobar¹ and Fabricio Marcillo³

¹ *Department of Architecture and Computer Technology, University of Granada, Spain*

² *Autonomous University of the State of Hidalgo, Pachuca, México*

³ *Faculty of Engineering Sciences, Quevedo State Technical University, Ecuador*

emails: `crodriguez@ugr.es`, `afdiaz@ugr.es`, `jortega@ugr.es`, `raulhp@ugr.es`,
`jjescobar@ugr.es`, `fmarcillo@correo.ugr.es`

Abstract

The realm of HPC systems lies in sharing computational resources efficiently. Their challenge is to turn massively large data into valuable information and meaningful knowledge. To accomplish this, I/O subsystems have to provide scalable bandwidth and capacity in order to deliver on the increasing demand for their requests. Emerging technologies, new programming paradigms and virtualized environments need novel ways to offer optimised solutions to support heavy data flows in storage services.

In this paper, we propose a distributed storage layer on computer nodes that can be used as a robust data storage service to handle intensive I/O operations. Preliminary experiments show that our platform outperforms other distributed data storage solutions.

Key words: Data storage, high performance computing, supercomputers, communication networks, file systems

1 Introduction

HPC centres are service providers, where multiple specialized computational resources provide different services. Some of these resources are designed to run simulations and generate data. Others provide post-processing or analysis of the generated data, while some are responsible for visualization of the raw or reduced data. The common denominator in

all of these scenarios is data. Data must be shared among these systems in an efficient manner.

I/O is mainly used in scientific applications to store output from simulations for later analysis, for implementing algorithms that process more data than can fit in system memory and must page data to and from disk and for checkpointing to save the state of application in case of system failure.

Modern distributed storage systems employ techniques that can help improve application performance, alleviate I/O bandwidth bottleneck, mask failures, and ensure data availability.

It is needed to develop both the theoretical and practical aspects of building efficient and scalable distributed storage that will scale and be tolerant of the inevitable node failures and service partitioning that come with multiple nodes. Raicu et al. [10] proposes a distributed storage architecture that will make exascale computing more tractable, touching virtually all disciplines in high-end computing and fueling scientific discovery. Chen et al.[1] proposes a Parallel, Reliable and Scalable Storage Software Infrastructure (PASSI) to support the design and prototyping of next-generation active storage environment.

Some tools have been created to modeling large-scale HPC I/O workload. Snyder et al.[12] have defined a novel workload abstraction layer that may be used by diverse tools to regenerate and analyze I/O workloads. They implemented three workload generators based on distinct representations of I/O workloads: I/O traces, synthetic I/O kernels, and I/O characterizations. They used a simulation model of an HPC storage system to analyse and compare each IOWA workload generation technique in detail, and they used an I/O replay engine to evaluate large-scale workloads on a production HPC storage system.

Ghoshal et al.[7] present their results in benchmarking the I/O performance over different cloud and HPC platforms to identify the major bottlenecks in existing infrastructure.

Multiple failure are inevitable in large storage systems, and designers must consider to avoid lost of data. The core technology for protecting data from failures is erasure coding, which has a rich 50+ year history stemming communication systems, and as such, can be confusing to the storage systems community. Plank [9] presents a primer on erasure coding as it applies to storage systems, and summarizes some interesting research on erasure coding.

In our paper, we provide a short background of a high performance data storage system in Section 2. We show a design overview in Section 3. We present some preliminary results in Section 4 and we conclude the paper in Section 5.

2 Background

A high performance data storage system is composed of several basic elements: different communication layers, storage units, data manipulation algorithms and control software.

All these elements are continually evolving to push the limits of existing technology. There are several aspects to managing a distributed high-performance storage system:

- Try to take full advantage of all resources: CPUs, storage and networks with a fast asynchronous client/server communication layer.
- Define a reliable system to manage resources: There are several software solutions: etcd[5], Consul[8], Zookeeper.
- Support different topologies: create storage volumes composed of several units and group them according to their performance: i.e: SSD for fast storage and HDD for slow operations.
- Redundancy management: To define how many units are needed to use for storage.
- Dynamic storage management: The less used files go to slow units.
- Use erasure codes to optimise integrity.

3 Design Overview

A distributed high-performance storage system requires to control resources in a efficient way and demands low latencies and high data bandwidth. Thus this complex system have to be decomposed into small services that solve different requirements. On a previous publication, we have shown a metadata system applied to HPC [11] and how to improve data sharing on Infiniband Networks [4].

The proposed model, AbFS3.L3 (AbFS3 Low Level Layer), is not a generic filesystem but rather a flexible platform to store any kind of data, defining a low level layer for a unified data storage (ie. object storage, files or blocks).

The main subsystem are:

- Resource management and service discovery system: It detects all available resources and changes in configuration. It supervises that all components are properly working. It is based on etcd [5].
- Fast data transfer system: It is a fluent data transport which adapts to different conditions (real and virtualized networks).
- Data balancing and redistribution: It is responsible for deciding how to distribute data among servers, replace data into new locations and recover accidental.
- Data storage API: It is the service that clients can access and provides cache and block control to accelerate interoperability.

Clients has a reduced configuration in order to achieve a coherent image and they "learn" new configuration profiles as they demand resources and, therefore, they need not be notified of general changes.

Clients can request operations to any server who will resolve the queries, and the server can "suggest" any other server to improve response times.

Administrator can select multiple configuration options to define redundancy, restrictions, migration policies or strict working conditions to support no single point of failure (NSPOF).

4 Results

The system has been tested in a cluster with 16 server nodes equipped with: Dual 2.27GHz Intel(R) Xeon(R) E5520 CPUs, 16GB RAM memory, 1TB Local Disk and OS CentOS 6.6. Our scenario has 4 servers and 10 clients. These nodes have two Broadcom Corporation NetXtreme II BCM5716 Gigabit Ethernet interfaces and a IBA7220 InfiniBand HCA.

We have compare our system with other implementations based on distributed filesystems, such as GlusterFS[3] and Ceph[2] with two different networks: Infiniband and Gigabit Ethernet.

Figure 1: Read bandwidth obtained

We show the throughput with a variety of block sizes ranging from 4 KB to 16 MB. Figure 1(a) shows read bandwidth obtained from a Gigabit Network and Figure 1(b) from an Infiniband and, Figure 2(a) shows write bandwidth using Gigabit Network and Figure 2(b) using Infiniband.

Figure 2: Write bandwidth obtained

Both figures show that our proposed system outperform Ceph and GlusterFS in all conditions: reads, writes, with diverse block sizes and different networks.

5 Conclusions and future work

In this paper we have presented a flexible platform for data storage in HPC systems. This system can be used as a robust low level interface to store and retrieve data efficiently. Preliminary experiments show that our platform outperforms other distributed data storage solutions. As future work, we want to combine this platform with an optimised metadata support and a virtual filesystem layer to perform fast I/O based on file operations.

Acknowledgements

This work has been partially supported by European Union FEDER and the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness TIN2015-67020-P and FPA2015-65150-C3-3-P.

References

- [1] Hsing-bung Chen and Song Fu. PASSI: A parallel, reliable and scalable storage software infrastructure for active storage system and I/O environments. In *34th IEEE*

International Performance Computing and Communications Conference, IPCCC 2015, Nanjing, China, December 14-16, 2015, pages 1–8, 2015.

- [2] Red Hat Inc. (Ceph Community). Ceph. <http://ceph.com>, 2017.
- [3] Red Hat Inc. (Gluster Community). Glusterfs. <https://www.gluster.org>, 2017.
- [4] Antonio F. Díaz, Julio Ortega, Andrés Ortiz, Godofredo Garay, and Alberto Prieto. Improving data sharing on Infiniband Networks. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Computational and Mathematical Methods in Science and Engineering, CMMSE*, pages 1326–1334, Jul 2014.
- [5] etcd Community. etcd. <https://github.com/coreos/etcd>, 2017.
- [6] The Apache Software Foundation. Hadoop distributed file system (hdfs). <https://wiki.apache.org/hadoop/HDFS>, 2017.
- [7] Devarshi Ghoshal, Richard Shane Canon, and Lavanya Ramakrishnan. I/o performance of virtualized cloud environments. In *Proceedings of the Second International Workshop on Data Intensive Computing in the Clouds, DataCloud-SC '11*, pages 71–80, New York, NY, USA, 2011. ACM.
- [8] HashiCorp. Consul. <http://consul.io>, 2017.
- [9] J. S. Plank. Erasure codes for storage systems: A brief primer. volume 38. Usenix Association, December 2013.
- [10] Ioan Raicu, Ian T. Foster, and Pete Beckman. Making a case for distributed file systems at exascale. In *Proceedings of the Third International Workshop on Large-scale System and Application Performance, LSAP '11*, pages 11–18, New York, NY, USA, 2011. ACM.
- [11] Cristina Rodríguez-Quintana, Antonio F. Díaz, Julio Ortega, Raúl H. Palacios, and Andrés Ortiz. Evaluating distributed metadata in HPC. In *Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on Computational and Mathematical Methods in Science and Engineering, CMMSE*, pages 965–972, 2015.
- [12] Shane Snyder, Philip H. Carns, Robert Latham, Misbah Mubarak, Robert B. Ross, Christopher D. Carothers, Babak Behzad, Huong Vu Thanh Luu, Surendra Byna, and Prabhat. Techniques for modeling large-scale HPC I/O workloads. In *Proceedings of the 6th International Workshop on Performance Modeling, Benchmarking, and Simulation of High Performance Computing Systems, PMBS 2015, Austin, Texas, USA, November 15, 2015*, pages 5:1–5:11, 2015.